

ELECTRONIC DANCE MUSIC SUBGENRE CLASSIFICATION USING MULTI-TEACHER KNOWLEDGE DISTILLATION WITH HETEROGENEOUS FEATURES

Rintaro URYU (瓜生倫太郎)¹, Shun SAWADA (澤田隼)¹, Kouichi KATSURADA (桂田浩一)¹, and Hidefumi OHMURA (大村英史)¹

¹Tokyo University of Science, Chiba, Japan

ABSTRACT

With the widespread adoption of music streaming services, automatic genre classification has become increasingly important in the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR). The explosive growth of digital music has made efficient and fine-grained genre classification essential for tasks such as music recommendation, playlist generation. However, research focusing on fine-grained genres remains limited, and publicly available datasets for EDM subgenre classification are limited. Moreover, subgenre classification remains a challenging task, due to the high degree of similarity between subgenres and the lack of clear definitions. In this study, we propose a multi-teacher learning model using response-based knowledge to improve classification accuracy while considering the relationships between subgenres. By utilizing knowledge from multiple teacher models, the proposed approach enables the representation of musical characteristics based on a broader range of features. To evaluate the proposed method, we constructed a custom dataset consisting of 3,000 tracks collected from top-100 lists across 30 EDM subgenres sourced from a website specializing in EDM tracks¹. Experimental results show that our method outperforms conventional feature fusion approaches, demonstrating the effectiveness of knowledge distillation in EDM subgenre classification. Furthermore, we analyze the contribution of each feature set and discuss the effectiveness of multi-teacher distillation in capturing complex subgenre characteristics.

Index Terms — Music genre classification, Knowledge Distillation, Feature Fusion, Audio signal processing

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, automatic genre classification has become increasingly important in the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) [1]. Music genres are widely used to represent the characteristics of songs and are influenced by cultural and geographical factors [2]. Additionally,

¹<https://www.beatport.com/>

Copyright: © 2025. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

genres serve as guidelines for composition and arrangement, as they are classified based on characteristics such as song structure, rhythm, melody, and harmony. Since the 2000s, research on automatic genre classification for top-level genres such as rock and classical music has been actively conducted, achieving high classification accuracy with deep learning-based approaches [3].

With the advancement of Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) and the widespread adoption of subscription-based music services, diverse cultural and regional music styles have merged [4], giving rise to numerous subgenres. Consequently, classification methods that focus solely on top-level genres struggle to adequately capture the complexity of modern music. Research on subgenre classification remains limited. The primary reasons for this are the inherent difficulty of the task and the lack of labeled datasets focusing on specific genres. However, subgenre classification is essential for the advancement of MIR [5]. Caparrini used a decision tree classifier based on acoustic statistical features to classify 29 EDM subgenres and demonstrated the importance of different features [6].

In general, deep learning-based approaches are known to be effective for learning from unstructured data such as audio [7]. However, subgenre classification requires considering multiple elements such as rhythm and timbre. In deep learning methods, Feature Fusion, which integrates multiple features for learning, poses a challenge due to its high computational cost. Knowledge distillation has been recognized as an effective approach for learning rich representations from features while maintaining low computational cost [8]. In this study, we propose a multi-teacher knowledge distillation model for feature fusion, with the goal of enhancing the classification performance of EDM subgenres.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Top-level Genre Classification

Top-level genre classification is the task of classifying basic music genres such as rock and jazz, and datasets like GTZAN are commonly used for this purpose. Research on top-level genre classification has been actively conducted since the 2000s [9] [10].

Ghildiyal et al. compared five models: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Multi-Layer Perceptron

(MLP), and Decision Tree, using the GTZAN dataset, which includes ten top-level genres. Their study demonstrated that CNN achieved the highest classification accuracy for music genre classification compared to the other models [7].

2.2 EDM Subgenre Classification

Subgenre classification is a task that classifies music at a finer granularity within a specific top-level genre. For example, in EDM, subgenres such as Trance, House, Drum & Bass, and Techno exist, each distinguished by differences in rhythm patterns, timbre, tempo, and structure. However, the boundaries between subgenres are often ambiguous, and there are many commonalities between different subgenres, making classification challenging. Currently, research on subgenre classification is less common than that on top-level genre classification.

Caparrini created a dataset consisting of 29 classes from Beatport², a music distribution platform specializing in EDM subgenres, and performed EDM subgenre classification using decision trees. In their study, Extremely Randomized Trees achieved a classification accuracy of 48.2% demonstrating that BPM information significantly contributes to classification performance in EDM subgenre classification [6].

EDM place emphasis on rhythm patterns and repetitive structures, which are characterized by steady beats such as the four-on-the-floor kick pattern, syncopated drum loops, and recurring musical motifs including drops, build-ups, and breakdowns. Dixon et al. conducted classification based on these features using ballroom dance music as their target [11]. Diakopoulos et al. applied these features to classify six EDM subgenres, achieving a classification accuracy of 75.2% [12]. Leimeister et al. targeted eight EDM subgenres and utilized source separation techniques to isolate bass drum and snare drum events, classifying based on rhythm pattern features. They demonstrated that using both BPM information and rhythm pattern features improved classification accuracy by 5% points compared to using only BPM information [13].

Panteli et al. proposed a method for analyzing the similarities between rhythm patterns and timbral features in EDM subgenres [14]. However, these methods consider only a limited number of classes, making them insufficient for practical applications.

Wei-Han Hsu et al. proposed a Feature Fusion method using mel-spectrograms and tempograms with a CNN model for EDM subgenre classification [15].

2.3 Knowledge Distillation

Knowledge Distillation (KD) is a technique originally proposed for model compression. By leveraging the knowledge learned by a teacher model during the training of a lightweight student model, it is known that the student model can achieve higher accuracy than training it independently [8] [16]. Traditionally, knowledge distillation has been primarily used for transferring knowledge from

large-scale models to smaller models within the same domain. A common approach is the Response-based Knowledge method, where the teacher model's output is treated as a soft target, and the student model is trained to match this output distribution.

The information obtained from training data using hard labels is limited to the direct correspondence between inputs and their correct labels, providing no insight into non-target classes. In contrast, the output of a trained teacher model provides prediction probabilities for all classes. These probability distributions contain subtle information, and leveraging them enables the student model to learn richer feature representations.

Knowledge distillation methods have also been applied to classification tasks [17]. Knowledge distillation has been shown to be effective in the field of music information retrieval (MIR), Sawada demonstrated that this method can implicitly interpret inter-class similarities and effectively transfer the knowledge of the teacher model in music signals [18]. Javier Nistal et al. proposed a model called "DarkGAN," which utilizes soft labels obtained from an audio tagging system as conditional information to achieve semantically interpretable and controllable audio synthesis [19].

3. EDM SUBGENRE CLASSIFICATION

This study aims to predict the EDM subgenre of a given song from unknown audio source data in the acoustic domain.

3.1 Dataset

Currently, there are few datasets available for audio signal-based EDM subgenre classification, and those that do exist cover only a limited number of classes. To the best of our knowledge, the publicly available dataset that covers the largest number of classes for EDM subgenre classification is provided by Caparrini et al. This dataset includes metadata for 29 subgenres of songs collected from Beatport as of February 2018.

However, this dataset was designed with decision tree-based methods in mind and utilizes hand-crafted acoustic statistical features. As a result, it is not well-suited for end-to-end deep learning-based classification tasks like those in this study.

Therefore, following the structure of Caparrini et al.'s dataset, we collected 100 tracks from the Top 100 song list of each subgenre (30 classes) on Beatport as of December 2024. Beatport provides song previews with a maximum length of 120 seconds and a minimum of 30 seconds. To standardize the audio file length, we collected only 30 seconds from each track and split them into two 15-second segments. For each of these samples, we computed audio features.

As a result, we provide a dataset containing 6,000 audio samples across 30 classes, each with its corresponding features. Since Beatport frequently updates the genres it features, the dataset constructed in this study differs substantially from that of Caparrini et al. The subgenres included

²<https://www.beatport.com/>

No.	Genres	No.	Genres	No.	Genres
1	AFRO HOUSE	11	ELECTRONICA	21	NU DISCO / DISCO
2	AMAPIANO	12	FUNKEY HOUSE	22	PROGRESSIVE HOUSE
3	BASS / CLUB	13	HARD DANCE / HARDCORE / NEO RAVE	23	PSY-TRANCE
4	BASS HOUSE	14	HARD TECHNO	24	TECH HOUSE
5	BREAKS / BREAKBEAT / UK BASS	15	HOUSE	25	TECHNO (PEAK TIME / DRIVING)
6	DANCE / POP	16	INDIE DANCE	26	TECHNO (RAW / DEEP / HYPNOTIC)
7	DEEP HOUSE	17	JACKIN HOUSE	27	TRANCE (MAIN FLOOR)
8	DRUM & BASS	18	MAINSTAGE	28	140 / DEEP DUBSTEP / GRIME
9	DUBSTEP	19	MELODIC HOUSE & TECHNO	29	TRAP / FUTURE BASS
10	ELECTRO (CLASSIC / DETROIT / MODERN)	20	MINIMAL / DEEP TECH	30	UK GARAGE / BASSLINE

Table 1. List of genres contained in our dataset.

Figure 1. Proposed model structure.

in this dataset are shown in Table 1.

3.2 Multi-Teacher Knowledge Distillation with Heterogeneous Features

The model structure of the proposed method is shown in Fig. 1. The method proposed in this study consists of the following two main processes.

Process 1: Each acoustic feature f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n is learned independently by n teacher models, where n represents the number of features (see Fig. 1 (a)).

Process 2: The outputs of each teacher model, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n are concatenated along the channel dimension and used to train the student model (see Fig. 1 (b)).

In this study, we use the distillation loss, expressed by Equation (1), as the loss function.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}} = \frac{1}{n+1} (\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL},i}) \quad (1)$$

\mathcal{L}_{CE} represents the loss between the student model and the training data, which is computed using Categorical Cross-Entropy. $\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL},i}$ represents the loss function between the logits of each teacher model and the student model, which is computed using Kullback-Leibler Divergence (KLD) and expressed as $\text{KL}(p||q)$. Here, $p = \text{softmax}(u_{\text{teacher}}/\tau)$ and $q = \text{softmax}(u_{\text{student}}/\tau)$, where τ is the temperature parameter of the softmax function. Additionally, u_{teacher} and u_{student} represent the logits of the teacher model and the student model, respectively.

In this study, ResNet50 is adopted as the teacher model. It is a CNN-based architecture that has proven effective in music genre classification tasks [20]. Additionally, ResNet18 is employed as the student model. This choice

is based on the fact that the output matrix of the teacher model, which serves as the input to the student model, is smaller in size compared to commonly used data such as mel-spectrograms. Applying a CNN model with an unnecessarily deep architecture to such data may lead to overfitting.

4. EVALUATION

4.1 Preprocessing

We preprocessed 6,000 audio samples in WAV format and extracted their acoustic features f_1, \dots, f_6 shown below.

Mel-spectrogram (f_1) is a time-frequency representation of an audio signal that reflects human auditory perception by mapping frequencies onto the mel scale. It is widely used in audio processing for tasks such as speech and music analysis, as it captures important timbral and structural features of a sound. We set the STFT window size to 2048, hop size to 512, and the number of mel filter bank bins to 128. As a result, the final output tensor size is $82,688 = 128 \times 646$.

Autocorrelation Tempogram (f_2) is a feature that analyzes the periodicity of a music signal, extracting tempo (BPM) and rhythmic patterns. By computing autocorrelation for each frame of the audio signal and visualizing periodicity over time, it effectively represents the rhythmic structure of a piece of music. We set the hop size between frames is set to 512, and the window length for autocorrelation is set to 128. As a result, the output tensor size is $82,688 = 128 \times 646$.

For the remaining features (f_3 to f_6), we employed a consistent hop size of 512 for the Fourier transform.

Onset Envelope (f_3) represents the changes in energy over time, capturing sudden increases in amplitude that indicate note onsets or percussive events. This feature is particularly useful in identifying rhythmic patterns, as it highlights moments where significant musical events occur. Output tensor size is $646 = 1 \times 646$.

Spectral Centroid (f_4) represents the center of mass of a sound spectrum and is often associated with the perceived brightness of a sound. It is widely used in music genre classification as it helps distinguish between different timbral characteristics of genres. Output tensor size is $646 = 1 \times 646$.

Spectral Contrast (f_5) measures the difference between peaks and valleys in a sound spectrum, capturing the distribution of energy across frequency bands. It is useful for

Figure 2. Model structure of late-fusion model (LF).

genre classification as it helps differentiate between musical textures and timbral characteristics. We used 6 bands, resulting in an output tensor size is $4,522 = 7 \times 646$

Zero Crossing Rate (ZCR) (f_6) represents the rate at which a signal changes its sign, indicating the frequency of zero crossings. It is particularly useful for distinguishing between percussive and harmonic sounds, making it effective for genre classification. The final output tensor size is $646 = 1 \times 646$

Here, all extracted features were standardized using Z-normalization. The feature extraction is performed using the Librosa library (librosa 0.10.2) in Python with a sampling rate of 22,050 Hz. The dataset is split into training and validation sets in an 8:2 ratio. To ensure the reliability of the model’s classification accuracy, we applied k-fold cross-validation with $k = 5$. Specifically, for each fold, the accuracy of the epoch with the lowest loss (determined by EarlyStopping) is used for evaluation. Additionally, to prevent data leakage, special care is taken when splitting the dataset.

4.2 Experimental Setup

In our study, to verify the effectiveness of the proposed Multi-Teacher Knowledge Distillation mode, we conducted comparative experiments with models that do not use KD and a model with additional features. we prepared the following four models.

- **LF (late-fusion model):** The model that performs learning via conventional late-fusion without using KD. It uses two features, Following the work of Wei-Han Hsu et al., we use mel-spectrograms and tempograms as input features [15]. Feature extraction is performed using ResNet-based feature extraction layers for each feature, and then they are concatenated along the channel dimension just before the fully connected layers. A 65-layer ResNet is used as the base model, and the number of parameters in the late-fusion model is designed to be similar to that in the KD2 model (Fig. 2).
- **Non-KL (model without KL divergence):** A model that learns using only the cross-entropy loss without employing KLD. Two features, mel-spectrogram and tempogram, are used as inputs to the teacher model, and the output of the teacher model serves as input to the student model (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Model structure of the model without KL divergence (Non-KL).

- **KD2 (KD with 2 features model):** A model that applies KD, using mel-spectrogram and tempogram as inputs to the teacher model, and using the output of the teacher model as input to the student model (Fig. 1).
- **KD6 (KD with 6 features model):** A model that applies KD by using six features as inputs to the teacher model. These feature are mel-spectrogram, tempogram, onset, spectral centroid, spectral contrast, and ZCR. The output of the teacher model is then used as input to the student model (Fig. 1).

Through the comparison between LF and KD2, we verify the effectiveness of the proposed method as a feature fusion approach. Additionally, by comparing Non-KL with KD2, we confirm the effectiveness of using KLD in the learning process. Furthermore, the comparison between KD2 and KD6 allows us to assess the effectiveness of increasing the number of features for EDM subgenre classification. The hyperparameters for this study are set as follows.

- Optimizer: SGD (momentum=0.9)
- Learning rate: 1.0×10^{-3}
- Batch size: 32
- Epoch: Training stops after 5 epochs if there is no update in validation loss.
- τ (temperature parameter): 15

4.3 Result and Discussion

The classification accuracies of each model are shown in Table 2. From the Table 2, LF achieved an accuracy of 48.83%, while KD2 recorded an accuracy of 54.37%, showing an improvement of 5.54%pt. This indicates that the proposed method is more effective in handling multiple features compared to the traditional late-fusion method. Additionally, Non-KL recorded an accuracy of 51.37%, which is 3.00%pt lower than KD2. This suggests that the KD loss plays a crucial role in the proposed method. Here, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show the learning curves of the loss observed through the 10th epoch for Non-KL and KD2, respectively. From the figures, it can be seen that in the case

Model	Param (M)	Input(teacher)						$u_{teacher}$	KD loss	Acc. (%)
		f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5	f_6			
LF	58.4	✓	✓							48.83
Non-KL	58.1	✓	✓					✓		51.37
KD2 (proposed)	58.1	✓	✓					✓	✓	54.37
KD6 (proposed)	97.7	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	57.20

Table 2. Accuracy for each model.

Figure 4. Loss curve for Non-KL.

Figure 5. Loss curve for KD2.

of Non-KL, the loss is increasing, while for KD2, the loss is gradually decreasing. This suggests that the KD loss has a regularizing effect, helping to prevent overfitting of the distillation model. From the Table 2, KD6 achieved an accuracy of 57.20%, with an improvement of 2.83%pt by using six features as inputs for the teacher model. These results indicate that increasing the number of input features can be expected to improve classification accuracy.

5. CONCLUSION

Fig. 6 shows the metrics matrices for KD2, using only the mel-spectrogram and only the tempogram, respectively. In the F1-score across all three cases, Amapiano and Drum & Bass record high values. This indicates that these genres are more distinctive in terms of timbre, BPM, and rhythm compared to other genres. Hardcore, when learned using only the mel-spectrogram or the tempogram individually, has an f1-score of less than 0.4 in both cases. However, in KD2, it records a score of 0.63. This indicates that by considering both timbral features and rhythmic/tempo features together, the genre, which could not be separated individ-

ually, was successfully distinguished. This means that the KD2 was able to learn more complex representations.

Fig. 7 is the confusion matrix for KD2. From the Fig. 7, it can be seen that the most frequent misclassification occurs when HardTechno is misclassified as Hardcore, with 20 samples. This is likely because both genres tend to favor high BPM and distorted sounds, making them musically similar. The key difference between these two genres is that HardTechno is characterized by heavy use of loops. It is believed that increasing the data amount or extending the data duration could help in distinguishing these genres. Additionally, the next most frequent misclassifications were 14 samples where DeepHouse was misclassified as DeepTech, and 13 samples where Afro House was misclassified as Progressive House. These cases can be attributed to the fact that the two misclassified genres belong to similar subgenres within the Deep or House categories. This suggests that the relationships between subgenres, as learned from the soft targets, are not entirely complete.

EDM subgenre classification is a crucial task for building optimal music recommendation systems in response to the increasingly complex nature of modern music. In this study, we propose a method for EDM subgenre classification using a machine learning model where the outputs of the softmax layers from multiple teacher models serve as inputs to the student model, and KD loss is used during training. This model outperforms traditional late-fusion learning in terms of classification accuracy. For the EDM subgenre classification task, this proposed model achieved a classification accuracy of approximately 57.2% by using six input features: Mel-spectrogram, tempogram, onset envelope, spectral centroid, spectral contrast, and zero-crossing rate.

Amapiano and Drum&Bass can be classified with high accuracy, while subgenres within the same group, such as House category, have not been fully separated. One of the challenges for future work is that in this study, each data segment is only 15 seconds long, which may not capture important characteristics, such as loop structures, crucial for EDM subgenre classification. Therefore, further verification using a larger dataset is required. Furthermore, although six features were used in this study, the feature selection was not sufficiently optimized. Some features, such as the tempogram and onset envelope, both represent rhythmic characteristics of music and therefore contain overlapping information. In addition, the effects of different feature combinations or increasing the number of features on classification accuracy also remain unexplored,

Figure 6. Metrics matrix for KD2 using mel-spectrogram and tempogram features individually. The x-axis corresponds to the genre numbers listed in Table 1.

Figure 7. Confusion matrix for KD6. The axes represent the genre numbers as shown in Table 1.

suggesting there is still room for improvement.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 25H01169.

6. REFERENCES

[1] R. Jaime and F. M. Julia, “Machine learning for music genre: multifaceted review and experimentation with audioset,” *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*,

vol. 55, no. 3, p. 469–499, Nov. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10844-019-00582-9>

[2] M. Charlotta, F. Richard, R. Peter, and P. Jeff, “The geography of music preferences,” *Journal of Cultural Economics*, vol. 42, 11 2018.

[3] N. Ndiatenda, A. Ritesh, and J. Ashwini, “Music genre classification: A review of deep-learning and traditional machine-learning approaches,” in *2021 IEEE International IOT, Electronics and Mechatronics Conference (IEMTRONICS)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.

[4] W. Liu, “The localization of global music and the diverse practices of modern european music festivals,” *Critical Humanistic Social Theory*, vol. 1, pp. 54–62, 10 2024.

[5] L. Tao and O. Mitsunori, “Music genre classification with taxonomy,” vol. 5, 04 2005, pp. v/197 – v/200 Vol. 5.

[6] C. Antonio, A. Javier, P.-M. Laura, and S.-H. Jaime, “Automatic subgenre classification in an electronic dance music taxonomy,” *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 269–284, 2020.

[7] G. Anirudh, S. Komal, and S. Sachin, “Music genre classification using machine learning,” in *2020 4th international conference on electronics, communication and aerospace technology (ICECA)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1368–1372.

[8] G. Jianping, Y. Baosheng, M. S. J, and T. Dacheng, “Knowledge distillation: A survey,” *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 129, no. 6, pp. 1789–1819, 2021.

[9] S. Nicolas, Z. Giorgio, and M. Daniel, “Automatic genre classification of music content: a survey,” *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 133–141, 2006.

- [10] F. Zhouyu, L. Guojun, T. K. Ming, and Z. Dengsheng, "A survey of audio-based music classification and annotation," *IEEE transactions on multimedia*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 303–319, 2010.
- [11] G. Fabien, D. Simon, P. Elias, and W. Gerhard, "Evaluating rhythmic descriptors for musical genre classification," in *Proceedings of the AES 25th International Conference*, vol. 196, 2004, p. 204.
- [12] D. Dimitri, V. Owen, H. Jordan, M. J. W, and K. Ajay, "21st century electronica: Mir techniques for classification and performance." in *ISMIR*, 2009, pp. 465–470.
- [13] L. Matthias, G. Daniel, and D. Christian, "Rhythmic classification of electronic dance music," in *Audio Engineering Society Conference: 53rd International Conference: Semantic Audio*. Audio Engineering Society, 2014.
- [14] P. Maria, R. Bruno, B. Niels, and H. Aline, "A model for rhythm and timbre similarity in electronic dance music," *Musicae Scientiae*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 338–361, 2017.
- [15] W.-H. Hsu, B.-Y. Chen, and Y.-H. Yang, "Deep learning based edm subgenre classification using mel-spectrogram and tempogram features," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.08862>
- [16] G. Hinton, O. Vinyals, and J. Dean, "Distilling the knowledge in a neural network," 2015.
- [17] B. A. Gabriel, T. K. C. Stéphane, E. H. Mohamed, and E. H. Mohammed, "Knowledge distillation in image classification: The impact of datasets," *Computers*, vol. 13, no. 8, 2024.
- [18] S. Sawada, "Symbolic-domain musical instrument classification using knowledge distillation from audio-teacher to symbolic-student," in *2024 32nd European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, 2024, pp. 191–195.
- [19] J. Nistal, S. Lattner, and G. Richard, "Darkgan: Exploiting knowledge distillation for comprehensible audio synthesis with gans," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.01216>
- [20] A. Safaa and K. A. Lameiras, "1d cnn architectures for music genre classification," in *2021 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, 2021, pp. 01–07.